

C– SHAPED CANAL CONFIGURATION & ITS MANAGEMENT:- A CASE SERIES

AUTHOR NAMES

1. Dr. Shweta R. Tugnayat

Post Graduate Student , Department Of Conservative Dentistry And Endodontics,
Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College And Hospital, Nagpur

2. Dr. Ambar Raut

Professor And Head Of Department , Department Of Conservative Dentistry And Endodontics,
Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College And Hospital, Nagpur.

3. Dr.Aarti Lamb

Post Graduate Student , Department Of Conservative Dentistry And Endodontics,
Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College And Hospital, Nagpur

4. Dr.Saniya Rege

Post Graduate Student , Department Of Conservative Dentistry And Endodontics,
Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College And Hospital, Nagpur

5. Dr.Maithilee Sapkal

Post Graduate Student , Department Of Conservative Dentistry And Endodontics,
Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College And Hospital, Nagpur

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR-

Dr.Shweta Tugnayat

Post Graduate Student , Department Of Conservative Dentistry And Endodontics,
Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College And Hospital, Nagpur.

Received: May 06, 2025

Accepted: Jun 04, 2025

Published: Jun 11, 2025

Abstract -Unusual root canal anatomy always poses a diagnostic and treatment challenge. Therefore a thorough knowledge of root canal anatomical variations along with proper diagnosis, treatment planning and clinical expertise is the key to their successful management.

The C-shaped root canal configuration is one such aberrant canal anatomy, common in the mandibular second molar. It often goes undetected and due to the intricate root canal configuration, it is often difficult to negotiate, debride and obturate such canals leading to failure of root canal treatment.

This paper presents a case report of C-Shaped root canal in mandibular second molars & its management .

Keywords-Anatomic variation, endodontic treatment , C-shaped canal, mandibular second molars, thermoplasticized obturation.

Introduction-

Ever since the identification of the C-shaped canal anatomy, various causes have been postulated for its formation. Earlier, teeth with C-shaped roots were likened to taurodonts; however, the definition of teeth that fit this description has been changed. Manning also conjectured that the C-shaped anatomy with separate canals could be the result of age changes due to deposition of dentin on the walls of the canal.² C-shaped canal anatomy was first documented by Cooke and Cox in mandibular second molar in 1979, though Weine et al reported that several clinicians had suggested its presence in lectures earlier.¹ This type of Canal configuration has a high prevalence in mandibular second molars (2.7%- 45.5%)²⁻⁵ and has also been reported in maxillary first molars (0.12%), maxillary third molars (4.7%), mandibular third molars (3.5%- 4%) and mandibular second premolars (1%).⁶⁻⁹

Melton et al's classification describes the following three types of C shaped canals continuous C shaped (C1), semicolon (C2) and separate canals (C3). This classification was further modified by Fan et al and the most prevalent type of C shape canal was single orifice with an uninterrupted "C " shape configuration according to this classification.³

Following features are a must for the canal morphology to be called as “C” shape: Fused roots, A longitudinal groove on the lingual or buccal surfaces of the root, At least one cross-section of the canal belongs to the C1, C2, or C3 configuration.¹²

It has been found that there is no correlation of C-shaped canal configuration with gender and also with age and tooth position but ethnic variation is found with highest frequency being reported in the East Asian population groups like Chinese population (29.7%) and Koreans (31.3%-45.5%).¹ The definition of the C-shaped root canal system is that the morphology of its horizontal cross section is in the form of a C, with canals which may or may not be separate.¹⁰

This anatomical variation results from the failure of Hertwig’s epithelial root sheath to develop or fuse in the furcation area in the developing stage of the teeth.²

Case 1-

A 29 year old female patient reported to the department with a chief complaint of pain on eating food in lower left back region of the tooth. No relevant medical history was present to the patient. Intraoral examination revealed carious # 37 with tenderness on percussion. Radiographically, a proximal radiolucency was seen in tooth 37 closely approximating the pulp space along with an associated widening of periodontal ligament space. Tooth was conical in shape with fused mesial and distal roots and a thin radiolucent line between them, with a suspected C-shaped canal.

After proper isolation and anesthesia, an access cavity was prepared and Fan et al C4 type canal anatomy was found. After working length determination cleaning and shaping was done with ProTaper rotary files (Dentsply Maillefer, Switzerland) up to F3 followed by circumferential filing with hand K files (Dentsply Maillefer, Switzerland). 5% sodium hypochlorite (Acrylates, India) was used as an endodontic irrigant which was activated with Endo activator (Dentsply Maillefer, Switzerland).

Calcium hydroxide (RC Cal Prime Dental Products, Thane, India) was placed as an intracanal medicament. After a week patient was recalled, radiograph was taken to confirm fit of the master cone and obturation was completed using warm vertical

compaction technique (Calamus, Dentsply Maillefer, Switzerland resin and post endodontic restoration was done with composite.

Fig- a.pre-operative Radiograph, b. access opening photograph c.working length radiograph, d. Master cone radiograph, e. Post obturation radiograph.

Case 2

A 24 year old female patient reported to the department with a chief complaint of pain on eating food in lower left back region of the tooth. No relevant medical history was present to the patient. Intraoral examination revealed carious # 47 with tenderness on percussion. Radiographically, a proximal radiolucency was seen in tooth 47 closely approximating the pulp space along with an associated widening of periodontal ligament space . Tooth was conical in shape with fused mesial and

distal roots and a 2 thin radiolucent line between them joining at apical one third, with a suspected C-shaped canal.

After proper isolation and anesthesia, an access cavity was prepared and Fan et al C3 type canal anatomy was found. After working length determination cleaning and shaping was done with ProTaper rotary files (Dentsply Maillefer, Switzerland) up to F3 followed by circumferential filing with hand K files (Dentsply Maillefer, Switzerland). 5% sodium hypochlorite (Acrylates, India) was used as an endodontic irrigant which was activated with Endo activator (Dentsply Maillefer, Switzerland).

Calcium hydroxide (RC Cal Prime Dental Products, Thane, India) was placed as an intracanal medicament. After a week patient was recalled, radiograph was taken to confirm fit of the master cone and obturation was completed using warm vertical compaction technique (Calamus, Dentsply Maillefer, Switzerland resin and post endodontic restoration was done with composite.

Fig- a.pre-operative Radiograph, b. access opening photograph c.working length radiograph, d. Master cone radiograph, e. Post obturation radiograph.

Discussion –The etiology for C-shaped morphology is failure of the Hertwig’s epithelial root sheath to fuse on the lingual or buccal root surface. The C-shaped root may also be formed by coalescence because of deposition of the cementum with time.²

Following features are a must for the canal morphology to be called as “C” shape: Fused roots, A longitudinal groove on the lingual or buccal surfaces of the root, At least one cross-section of the canal belongs to the C1, C2, or C3 configuration.¹²

Challenges faced during the C- shaped canal configuration treatment - Management of this type of canal configuration is a highly challenging task for a clinician. However, with the advent of newer technical advancements in the form of Cone beam CT scan, Operating microscopes, sonic, ultrasonic irrigation devices and thermoplasticized obturation technique successful management of this anatomical aberration has been achieved. Points to be considered in management of C shaped canal morphology: Preoperative radiograph will show fused roots so additional 20° mesial or the distal angulation will be useful to deduct this configuration. Isthmus preparation should be restricted till no 25 file and anti-curvature filing is recommended to avoid strip perforations. Avoid use of Gates-Glidden drills for the same. Irrigation supplemented with ultrasonic agitation is the key to success as it would clean the inaccessible areas of the complex “C” shape anatomy. To ensure proper placement of the master cones in C shaped canals, Walid’s technique involves placing the master points simultaneously in the C-shaped canal. A large plugger is placed on one of the seared master points while the other master point is down packed with a smaller plugger.¹³ Thermoplasticized obturation technique is preferred as it ensures a better 3 dimensional fill than cold lateral compaction technique.

Conclusion-

Knowledge of different possible alterations in the internal anatomy of teeth is important for successful endodontic therapy. The C-shaped canal system

tends to vary considerably in their anatomical configuration and thus leads to difficulties in debridement, cleaning, shaping & obturation.

The diagnosis, treatment planning , & treatment procedure should be carefully done in these cases. The C-shaped root canal configuration has an ethnic predilection and a high prevalence rate in mandibular second molars.

For successful endodontic management proper diagnosis, sound knowledge about aberrant root canal anatomy, a thorough chemo-mechanical preparation with a 3-dimensional obturation of C-shaped canals is essential to ensure a good long term prognosis.

References-

1. Fernandes M, Ataide ID, Wagle R. C-shaped root canal configuration: A review of literature. *J Conserv Dent.* 2014;17;p. 312–9.
2. Manning SA. Root canal anatomy of mandibular second molars. Part II: C shaped canals. *Int Endod J.* 1990;23:40–5.
3. Fan B, Cheung GS, Fan M, Gutmann JL, Bian Z. C-shaped Canal System in Mandibular Second Molars: Part I—Anatomical Features. *J Endod.* 2004;30(12):899–903.
4. Gulabivala K, Opananon A, Ng YL, Alavi A. Root and canal morphology of Thai mandibular molars. *Int Endod J.* 2002;35(1):56–62.
5. Jin GC, Lee SJ, Roh BD. Anatomical study of C-shaped canals in mandibular second molars by analysis of computed tomography. *J Endod.* 2006;32:10–3.
6. Sidow SJ, West LA, Liewehr FR, Loushine RJ. Root canal morphology of human maxillary and mandibular third molars. *J Endod.* 2000;26;p. 6758.

7. Yu X, Guo B, Li KZ, Zhang R, Tian YY, Wang H. Conebeam computed tomography study of root and canal morphology of mandibular premolars in a western Chinese population. *BMC Med Imaging*. 2012;12:18.
8. Kuzekanani M, Haghani J, Nosrati H. Root and canal morphology of mandibular third molars in an Iranian population. *J Dent Res Dent Clin Dent Prospects*. 2012;6:858.
9. Cleghorn BM, Christie WH, Dong CC. Root and root canal morphology of the human permanent maxillary first molar: A literature review. *J Endod*. 2006;32:81321.
10. Vieira MVB, Vieira MM, Pileggi R. C-shaped canal": an anatomical variation. *RBO*. 1998;55(4):204–8.
11. Elumalai D, Kumar A, Tewari RK, Mishra SK, Iftekhar H, Andrabi SM, et al. Management of C-shaped root canal configuration with three different obturation systems. *Eur J Gen Dent*. 2015;4(1):25–8.
12. Yadav K, Ataide IDND, Fernandes M, Lambor R. Management of C shaped canals: 3 case reports. *Int J Contemp Med Res*. 2016;3(5):1340–2.
13. Walid N. The use of two pluggers for the obturation of an uncommon C-shaped canal. *J Endod*. 2000;26:4224